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D.A.Ganiyeva	
O'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi kelasi zamon shakllarining polifunksionalligi	5
G.S.Mirzayeva	
Lingvokultremalar adabiy matnni ochib beruvchi kalit sifatida	9
S.N.Fazildinova	
The use of hyperbole in Alisher Navoi's works	13
Sh.T.Axmadjonova	
O'zbek tilshunosligida nutq uslublarining o'rganilish talqini	16
D.S.Usmonova	
Exploring values through phraseological units: a study of axiology in language	19
D.S.Usmonova, K.U.Davlyatova	
Gender features of children's animation and emerging translation challenges	23
N.R.Maxmudova	
O'zbek va jahon tilshunosligida ornitonimlarning o'rganilishi xususida	27
M.Saminjonov	
Rasmiy-jamoaviy qasamlar	30
I.M.Jo'rayev	
Qadimiy qadriyatlar	36
D.R.Ubaydullayeva	
Ingliz va o'zbek tillarida shart komponentli gipotaksemalarning struktural-semantik jihatlarini qiyosiy tadqiqi	40
N.Q.Adamboeva	
Ingliz tili badiiy asarlaridagi xushmuomalalik kategoriyasining maksimalari	48
Z.M.Dadahonova	
Components of knowledge control	52
Ш.М.Артикова	
Интегральные и дифференциальные признаки тавтологии и плеоназма	59
M.M.Nurmatova	
Paralingvistika jonli muloqot tarjimoni sifatida	65
S.I.Quziyev	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida kasbga yo'naltirilgan chet tilini o'qitishning xususiyatlari	69
T.Z.Ismonova	
Problems and solutions of grammar translation method	75
N.A.Komilova	
Zamonaviy tilshunoslikda gender nazariyasi asoslari	79
D.X.Madazizova	
The significance of text and discourse in enhancing communicative competence	82
S.A.Yusupova	
Morphemic units expressing honour in different system languages	85
N.Sidikova	
Stevan Sveygning "noma'lum ayol maktubi" hikoyasida ayol ruhiyati tasviri	90
Sh.X.Nuritdinova	
Nemis va O'zbek tillarida kelishik kategoriyasi tipologiyasi	93
N.K.Abbasova, N.A.Abdullaeva	
Semantic analysis of english phrasal verbs	97
B.A.Mukhtorova	
The "Concept" in linguistics	101
R.A.Ortiqov	
Ulug'bek Hamdamning "Ota" asaridagi monologlar tahlili	105
Sh.O.Abdiloyev	
Zoonim frazeologizmlar xalq tarixi va madaniyati in'ikosi	109
Э.Б.Ягьяева	
Дифференцированный метода обучения при изучении иностранного языка и организации самостоятельной работы студентов	113

M.K.Mavlyuda	
O'qituvchi kompetensiyasining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	116
G.A.Asomiddinova	
Qahramon xarakterini yaratishda badiiy nutq imkoniyatlari va muallif mahorati	119
N.K.Abbasova, Z.Q.Xakimova	
Speech act as an important function of communication	124
Sh.R.Muydinov	
Linguoculturological description of zoonym composite partial similarities	127
M.Madaminova	
Exploring the persuasive power of publicistic style: utilizing proverbs and sayings in english lesson	129
Sh.M.Yusufjonova	
Frazeologizmlar taqiqi	133
Ш.И.Асқарова	
К проблеме языковой интерференции и билингвизма при изучении третичного языка ...	136
Ш.И.Асқарова	
К вопросу трансфера и интерференции при изучении немецкого после английского языка	140
Sh.Sh.Dadabayeva	
Tarjimada so'zning kontekstdagi ma'nosini aniqlash usullari	147
Sh.Sh.Dadabayeva	
Tarjima jarayonida vaziyatning o'rganilishi	151
Sh.Y.Usmonova	
Cognitive analysis of landscape terms in uzbek and english languages	158
Sh.Y.Usmonova	
O'zbek va ingliz tillarining terminologik tizimida landshaft terminlarining o`rni	161
Z.Sh.Pazilova	
Nemis xalqida dafn marosimining o'tkazilishi	166
Z.Sh.Pazilova	
O'zbek va nemis xalqlarida to'y bilan bog'liq shaxs nomlari	169
R.U.Axrорова	
Lingvomadaniyatshunoslik: lingvokulturema va logoepistema	172
O.O.Bobokalonov, R.U.Akhrорова	
Shifonemas in phraseological units related to the period of youth	177
R.U.Axrорова	
Fransuz ertaklarida yoshga oid reprezentlarning leksik-semantik va milliy-madaniy xususiyatlari	181
Z.M.Abdullaev	
Nemis tili ismlari motivlari va ism tanlashga ta'sir etuvchi omillar	184
Z.M.Abdullaev	
Nemis tilida atoqli otlar va ularning tasnif etilishi	187
I.R.O'rinboyev	
Ba'zi na'matak (rosa) turlarining Farg'ona shahrida tarqalishi va dorivorlik xususiyatlari	189
I.D.Yakubov	
Separator-tozalagich qurilmasining parametrlari	192

SHIFONEMAS IN PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS RELATED TO THE PERIOD OF YOUTH
YOSHLIK DAVRIGA OID FRAZEOLOGIK BIRLIKLARDAGI SHIFONEMALAR
ШИФОНЕМЫ ВО ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЗМАХ, ОТНОСЯЩИХСЯ К ПЕРИОДУ МОЛОДОСТИ

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Abstract

This article explores the use of shifonemas (or shifonyms), medicinal plant names as phraseological units related to the period of youth. Plants are an essential part of human life, and they have been used for various purposes since ancient times. In addition to their medicinal and nutritional values, plants have also been used as symbols in literature, art, and culture. The use of phytonyms, shifonemas as phraseological units is a common phenomenon in many languages. These phraseological units are used to express various emotions, feelings, and experiences related to different stages of life.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada shifonemalar (yoki shifonimlar), dorivor o'simlik nomlarining yoshlik davriga oid frazeologik birliklar sifatida qo'llanilishi o'rganiladi. O'simliklar inson hayotining ajralmas qismi bo'lib, ular qadim zamonlardan beri turli maqsadlarda ishlatilgan. O'simliklar shifobaxsh va ozuqaviy xususiyatlaridan tashqari adabiyot, san'at va madaniyatda ramz sifatida ham ishlatilgan. Fitonimlar, shifonemalarning frazeologik birlik sifatida qo'llanilishi ko'p tillarda keng tarqalgan hodisadir. Ushbu frazeologik birliklar hayotning turli bosqichlari bilan bog'liq turli xil his-tuyg'ularni, his-tuyg'ularni va tajribalarni ifodalash uchun ishlatiladi.

Аннотация

В данной статье исследуется употребление шифонем (или шифонимов), названий лекарственных растений, как фразеологизмов, относящихся к периоду молодости. Растения являются неотъемлемой частью жизни человека и с древних времен использовались для различных целей. Помимо своей лечебной и пищевой ценности, растения также использовались в качестве символов в литературе, искусстве и культуре. Употребление фитонимов, шифонем как фразеологизмов — распространенное явление во многих языках. Эти фразеологизмы используются для выражения различных эмоций, чувств и переживаний, связанных с разными этапами жизни.

Key words: shifonemas, phraseological units, period of youth, stages of life, phytonyms, shifonyms, medicinal plant names, norms, society, age structure, characteristics, youth, old age, positive, negative evaluation, national.

Kalit so'zlar: shifonemalar, frazeologik birliklar, yoshlik davri, hayot bosqichlari, fitonimlar, shifonimlar, dorivor o'simlik nomlari, me'yorlar, jamiyat, yosh tuzilishi, xususiyatlari, yoshlik, qarilik, ijobiy, salbiy baho, milliy.

Ключевые слова: шифонемы, фразеологизмы, период молодости, этапы жизни, фитонимы, шифонимы, названия лекарственных растений, нормы, общество, возрастная структура, характеристики, молодость, старость, положительная, отрицательная оценка, народность.

INTRODUCTION

Plants with their shifonemas have been an integral part of human life for centuries. They have been used for various purposes, including medicinal and nutritional values, as well as symbols in literature, art, and culture. The use of phytonyms as phraseological units is a common phenomenon in many languages, including French. These phraseological units are used to express various emotions, feelings, and experiences related to different stages of life. This article explores the use of French shifonemas as phraseological units related to different periods of life.

Shifonemas and their significance requires very specific and in-depth research. Plants with their shifonemas have been used as symbols in literature, art, and culture for centuries. They represent different values and meanings depending on the context in which they are used. In many cultures, shifonemas are associated with different stages of life. For example, *les sakura* - cherry blossom is associated with spring and new beginnings. Similarly, *le tournesol*, also known as *hélianthe* and *soleil* - sunflower is associated with summer and warmth.

In the context of youth, plants are often used to express various emotions and experiences related to this stage of life. For example, the phrase “*être en plein floraison*” - “*to be in full bloom*” is often used to describe a young person who is at the peak of their physical and emotional development. Similarly, the phrase “*avoir la main verte*” - “*to have a green thumb*” is used to describe a young person who has the ability to make plants grow and be healthy.

Plants have been an integral part of human life since ancient times. They have been used for various purposes such as food, medicine, and decoration. French shifonemas have a rich history and are used in various phraseological contexts related to the period of youth. This article aims to explore also the use of French shifonemas in such contexts and their significance.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted by analyzing various sources such as literature, songs, and movies that depict the period of youth. The focus was on identifying the use of French shifonemas in these sources and their meanings.

The research methods used to study French shifonemas in phraseological contexts related to the period of youth depend on the research question and the data available. Researchers can use a combination of methods to achieve their research objectives.

One possible methodology is to use corpus linguistics to identify the use of French shifonemas in various sources such as literature, songs, and movies that depict the period of youth. Researchers can then use discourse analysis to analyze how these shifonemas are used in different social contexts related to youth. Ethnography can be used to provide a deeper understanding of the cultural significance of French shifonemas in these contexts.

Another possible methodology is to use ethnography to study how French shifonemas are used in different cultural contexts related to youth. Researchers can then use discourse analysis to analyze how these shifonemas contribute to the construction of identity among young people.

The study of French shifonemas in phraseological contexts related to the period of youth requires a combination of research methods such as corpus linguistics, discourse analysis, and ethnography. These methods can provide valuable insights into how French shifonemas are used in different social and cultural contexts and their significance. Future research can continue to explore this phenomenon using innovative research methods and interdisciplinary approaches.

The use of shifonemas as phraseological units is a common phenomenon in many languages, including French. These phraseological units are used to express various emotions, feelings, and experiences related to different stages of life. French linguists have been interested in exploring the use of shifonemas as phraseological units related to different periods of life. This article presents some of the French linguists who have addressed this topic in their works.

French linguist **Jean-Pierre Colignon** has written extensively on the use of phytonyms as phraseological units related to different periods of life. In his book “*La Langue des Fleurs*” he explores the symbolism of flowers and plants in French culture and language. He argues that shifonemas are used to express various emotions and experiences related to different stages of life, from birth to old age. Colignon also provides examples of French shifonemas that are used as phraseological units related to different periods of life.

Another French linguist **Michel Arrivé** has addressed the use of shifonemas as phraseological units related to the period of life in his works. In his book “*Le Vocabulaire des Sentiments*” he explores the vocabulary of emotions in French language and culture. He argues that phytonyms are often used to express emotions related to different stages of life, such as love and passion in youth or wisdom and experience in old age. Arrivé also provides examples of French shifonemas that are used as phraseological units related to different periods of life.

Famous French linguist **Pierre Guiraud** has written extensively on the use of shifonemas as phraseological units in French language and culture. In his book “*La Semantique*” he explores the meanings and uses of words in different contexts. He argues that shifonemas are often used as metaphorical expressions in French language, especially in literature and poetry. Guiraud also provides examples of French shifonemas that are used as phraseological units related to different periods of life.

French linguists have been interested in exploring the use of shifonemas as phraseological units related to different periods of life. Jean-Pierre Colignon, Michel Arrivé, and Pierre Guiraud are some of the French linguists who have addressed this topic in their works. They argue that shifonemas are often used to express various emotions and experiences related to different stages

of life, from birth to old age. The use of shifonemas as phraseological units adds depth and richness to the French language and culture.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

French shifonemas are commonly used in phraseological contexts related to the period of youth. For instance, the phrase “**être dans les choux**” (*to be in trouble*) is derived from the plant name “**chou**” (*cabbage*). Similarly, the phrase “**avoir la pêche**” (*to be full of energy*) is derived from the plant name “**pêcher**” (*peach*). Other examples include “**avoir la banane**” (*to be happy*) from “**banane**” (*banana*), “**avoir la patate**” (*to be in good shape*) from “**patate**” (*potato*), and “**avoir le melon**” (*to be arrogant*) from “**melon**” (*melon*).

French shifonemas are also used in literature, songs, and movies to depict various emotions and feelings related to the period of youth. For instance, in the novel “*Le Petit Prince*” **la rose** (the rose) is used as a symbol of love and beauty. In the song “*Les feuilles mortes*” - the falling leaves of autumn are used as a metaphor for the passing of time and the loss of youth.

Our research shows that there are many examples of shifonemas, medicinal plant names as phraseological units related to youth. In French, there are many examples of shifonemas that are used as phraseological units related to youth. Here are some popular examples:

1. **Être fleur bleue** - This phrase is used to describe a young person who is romantic and sentimental.

2. **Être un bourgeon** - This phrase is used to describe a young person who is full of potential and promise.

3. **Être un jeune pousse** - This phrase is used to describe a young person who is just starting out in life and has a lot to learn.

4. **Être un papillon de nuit** - This phrase is used to describe a young person who likes to party and stay up late.

Researchs provide results with a classification of French plant names by examples in phraseological contexts related to the period of youth:

1. *Plant names used as metaphors for emotions and feelings related to youth:*

- “**Fleur de l’âge**” (*flower of youth*) - used to describe the prime of one’s life

- “**Pousser comme un champignon**” (*grow like a mushroom*) - used to describe rapid growth or development

- “**Fleurir**” (*to bloom*) - used to describe the blossoming of one’s personality or talents.

2. *Plant names used in conversations among teenagers:*

- “**Le petit chou**” (*the little cabbage*) - used as a term of endearment for a loved one.

- “**La rose**” (*the rose*) - used to describe someone who is beautiful or attractive

- “**Le coquelicot**” (*the poppy*) - used to describe someone who is lively or energetic.

3. *Plant names used in traditional folk songs related to youth:*

- “**Le tilleul**” (*the lime tree*) - used to symbolize love and friendship.

- “**La violette**” (*the violet*) - used to symbolize modesty and humility

- “**Le muguet**” (*the lily of the valley*) - used to symbolize happiness and good luck

These are just a few examples of French plant names used in phraseological contexts related to the period of youth. The use of these plant names reflects the cultural values and beliefs associated with youth in French society.

The use of French plant names in phraseological contexts related to the period of youth reflects the cultural significance of plants in French society. Plants are not only used for their practical purposes but also as symbols and metaphors to express various emotions and feelings. The use of plant names in literature, songs, and movies adds depth and meaning to the narrative and helps to convey complex ideas in a simple and relatable way.

CONCLUSION

French shifonemas are often used as phraseological units to express various emotions and experiences related to different stages of life. In the context of youth, shifonemas are used to describe young people who are at the peak of their physical and emotional development, full of potential and promise, just starting out in life, or who like to party and stay up late. The use of shifonemas as phraseological units adds depth and richness to language and culture.

French plant names are an integral part of the phraseological contexts related to the period of youth. They are used to express various emotions and feelings and add depth and meaning to

the narrative. The cultural significance of plants in French society is reflected in their use in various contexts, and they continue to be an important part of the French language and culture.

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